

The Raman Fingerprint of Quartz

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Abstract

Here we consider a processing method for Raman spectra, suitable to determine the positions of the peaks and their shoulders. This processing is based on the behavior of the first derivative. It can be used as a preprocessing method for a further fitting of the spectrum by means of Tsallis q-Gaussian functions (Sparavigna, 2023). The spectra considered are those of Quartz from RRUFF database.

Keywords: Raman spectroscopy, Tsallis q-Gaussian distribution.

In previous studies (Sparavigna, 2023) we have demonstrated that the Tsallis q-Gaussian¹ functions, in the symmetric and asymmetric forms, are suitable for being used as lineshapes of the Raman spectral components. In the q-Gaussian analysis, the position of the center of the peaks is determined according to the best fit by means of an iterative procedure. The iteration starts from initial positions which can be determined, for instance, by the approach here proposed. The processing here described of spectral data is based on the first derivative behavior. In general, what is defined as the “first derivative spectrum” (Mosier-Boss et al., 1995), may be used for spectral comparison.

Some points of identification, such the positions of peaks and shoulders and their relative intensities, constitute the Raman “fingerprint” of a given material, which can be useful for its classification. We can tell that we have a fingerprint matching when the peak positions are almost the same. In the case that the spectrum has little detail, for instance it is possessing a few broad peaks with shoulders, a further investigation can be useful, and a fitting with q-Gaussians can be relevant.

The problem of determining this fingerprint seems being requiring further studies, as shown by a recent publication about the Raman spectral mineral classification obtained by means of the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) (Berlanga et al., 2022). The aim of Berlanga and coworkers is that of having a method which can allow the Martian rovers’ instrumentation to automatically identify the minerals. This task is fundamental because of the time delay of communication between Earth and Mars. Berlanga and coworkers tell that “Most peak detection algorithms identify peaks based solely on amplitude, sacrificing low-amplitude peak detection, and increasing the rate of false positives in low signal to noise situations (Du et al., 2006; Yang et al., 2009). Accordingly, Berlanga et al. used the wavelet space “to

¹ See please the works by Hanel, Tsallis and Umarov mentioned in the References, to appreciate the physical statistics method on which the q-Gaussian functions are based.

simplify peak matching, increase the apparent SNR [signal-to-noise ratio], and bypass baseline removal and peak smoothing steps”.

In the Figure 3 of Berlanga et al. we can see just that wavelets are identifying five main peaks of Quartz, Albite, Hornblende and Biotite. Let us consider Quartz and the spectra of it provided by RRUFF database (Lafuente et al., 2015), to understand how many peaks we must deal with in any fitting approach we want to use (the RRUFF database is also used by Berlanga and coworkers). At the web page <https://rruff.info/Quartz> we can find 10 spectra. R040031, R050125 and R060604 are spectra obtained from oriented samples (we use the processed 0° depolarized data). X080015, X080016, R100134, R110104, R110108, R150074 and R150091 are spectra obtained from unoriented samples (we use the data for 532 nm exciting laser). Here we propose an approach based on the “first derivative spectrum”.

To determine the position of the peaks, the steps are as follow. 1) A scaling is made to have the spectrum with its maximum intensity at value 1. 2) Data are represented as a function of increasing Raman shift. 3) A “peak” is a part of the spectrum where it has a maximum, then the first derivative of the function is positive before and negative after the peak. 4) The first derivative is taken by the "simple difference" method. 5) If necessary, the spectrum and the first derivative are smoothed by Savitsky-Golay method. 6) A threshold t for the intensity is chosen, so that only the peaks where the data have an intensity above the given threshold are considered. 7) For each intensity peak, the first derivative spectrum has a peak (positive values) and a trough (negative values). The widths of them, a_left and a_right as in the Fig.1, are evaluated. If both a_left and a_right are larger than a given value w , the peak of intensity spectrum is considered as a good one. A proper choice of w allows reducing the number of false positive. However, other statements based on a_left and a_right can be decided.

Fig.1: A peak of a Raman spectrum and its first derivative. The derivative has a peak and a trough, positive and negative. The width a_left and a_right are considered as in the figure.

Here in the following plots 2-11, the peaks of the RRUFF spectra are shown in the semi log scale. The blue line is representing the intensity threshold.

Fig. 2: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

Fig. 3: Intensity threshold at 4/1000.

Fig. 4: Intensity threshold at 10/1000.

Fig.5: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

Fig.6: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

Fig.7: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

Fig.8: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

Fig.9: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

Fig.10: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

Fig.11: Intensity threshold at 5/1000.

From the plots, let us pass to the following Table I.

109.6	121.3	130.5	146.5	208.2	265.9	356.4	404.2	466.1	505.7	544.0	698.4	810.2	861.9	1082.8	1159.4	1230.9
62.3		126.0		204.5		353.7	392.9	463.4			694.4			1062.5	1079.1	1158.1
		129.0	146.9	207.0	264.9	355.5	395.7	403.5	465.4	510.9	701.1	809.9		1082.3	1160.5	
		128.1		204.8	264.1	355.2	394.3	402.9	464.2	516.7	696.5	807.9	1045.1	1081.8	1158.9	
		128.1		204.8	263.6	355.2	394.3	399.1	464.6		695.0	795.9	1065.4		1160.8	
				204.3	264.6	354.8	402.5	464.2	508.1		697.1	808.4		1080.8	1157.5	1228.8
				204.8	264.5	355.2	393.7	464.6	521.5	532.1	696.0	806.0	1070.2		1161.3	1232.6
109.8	121.4			204.3	265.0	355.7	403.4	464.6	509.0		697.5	808.8		1082.2	1158.9	1230.7
		128.8		206.0	246.9	265.8	356.4	394.5	403.6	465.4	509.2	696.8	809.6	1083.0	1160.6	
		129.8	147.2	206.5	265.3	343.4	356.4	381.9	395.5	465.8	510.2	696.8	798.5	1068.0	1162.5	

Table 1: From top to bottom, the peaks of R040031, R050125, R060604, X080015, X080016, R100134, R110104, R110108, R150074, R150091 spectra are given. The peaks evidenced in red are present in all the spectra.

In the Table 2, the relative intensities of the five peaks evidenced in the previous Table 1 are given.

Spectrum R040031		Spectrum R050125		Spectrum R060604		Spectrum X080015		Spectrum X080016	
Shift	Intensity								
208.231	0.252	204.488	0.224	207.006	0.251	204.787	0.258	204.787	0.243
356.365	0.062	353.659	0.063	355.510	0.062	355.207	0.056	355.207	0.030
466.100	1.0	463.352	1.0	465.380	1.0	464.166	1.0	464.648	1.0
698.375	0.007	694.364	0.125	701.117	0.010	696.546	0.009	695.582	0.015
1159.453	0.014	1158.093	0.036	1160.478	0.022	1158.896	0.015	1160.825	0.027
Spectrum R100134		Spectrum R110104		Spectrum R110108		Spectrum R150074		Spectrum R150091	
Shift	Intensity								
204.333	0.285	204.754	0.254	204.272	0.332	205.973	0.246	206.455	0.201
354.753	0.072	355.174	0.075	355.656	0.072	356.394	0.080	356.394	0.041
464.193	1.0	464.615	1.0	464.615	1.0	465.352	1.0	465.834	1.0
697.056	0.012	696.031	0.014	697.477	0.017	696.768	0.007	696.768	0.018
1157.478	0.017	1161.273	0.027	1158.863	0.026	1160.564	0.013	1162.493	0.037

Table 2

Table 1 and Table 2 are representing the “fingerprints” of quartz. We can decide to use just five peaks, as in Berlanga, 2022, or add further details from the Tables, increasing the number of peaks and also considering the relative intensity. At these two tables, we could also add details about asymmetries, by means of a_{left} and a_{right} parameters.

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